

Quadro 12 – Tendências e Lacunas identificadas

ID	Classificação	Evidência Identificada	Evidência dos Estudos
[A02]	Lacuna	Ausência de métricas padronizadas para avaliar a colaboração entre humanos e IAG em equipes de projeto.	"Yet, the performance measures for its collaboration with humans in project teams are not established. [...] there is still a dearth of research on the application of GenAIs in the business sector, and the way of measuring its performance when integrated into PTs."
[A03]	Tendência	Crescente interesse em Sistemas Multiagentes e LLMs para resolução de problemas complexos, tomada de decisão e planejamento.	"Multi-Agent Large Language Models (LLMs) are gaining significant attention for their ability to harness collective intelligence in complex problem-solving, decision-making, and planning tasks."
[A07]	Tendência	Expansão do uso da IAG em inovação, prototipação e sistemas de gestão do conhecimento.	"The article highlights a large variety of use cases for generative AI ranging from user journey mapping to idea generation and prototyping and foreshadows the promising role LLMs may play in future knowledge management systems."
[A08]	Lacuna	Baixa maturidade organizacional e escassez de pesquisas sobre adoção da IAG no ambiente corporativo.	"Despite the hype about and widespread experimentation with ChatGPT, research on the use of generative AIs in the corporate world is still scarce. [...] Organizations are still in the early stages of tapping the potential of generative AI."
[A09]	Lacuna	Limitações e baixa adoção da IAG para geração automática de cronogramas de projetos.	"Few studies have investigated the application of natural language to develop project schedules. [...] However, the technology still has limitations, and further development is needed before it can be widely adopted in the industry."
[A05]	Lacuna	Falta de estudos comparativos entre decisões geradas por IAG e decisões humanas em gerenciamento de projetos.	"The application of generative AI in project management holds the promise of automating repetitive tasks, optimizing resource allocation, and improving risk assessment. [...] There are no comparative studies of generative AI and human decision-making."
[A13]	Lacuna	Necessidade de compreender fatores que influenciam a adoção e adaptação da IAG por gerentes de projetos.	"A significant gap remains in the research concerning the managerial perspective, particularly those factors influencing the adoption of these technologies by project managers."
[A14]	Tendência	Crescente aplicação da IAG em gerenciamento de projetos de construção para aumentar eficiência e precisão.	"Recent research indicates that AI's application in construction project management could significantly enhance efficiency and accuracy. [...] The general understanding of how generative AI solutions could be used to revolutionize this domain is still insufficient."
[A15]	Lacuna	Subexploração da IAG para otimização integrada de custos em ambientes organizacionais complexos.	"Despite these advancements, the application of Generative AI in holistic cost optimization remains underexplored. [...] Most existing frameworks focus on specific cost components without considering their interdependencies."
[A16]	Lacuna	Falta de integração eficiente de modelos generativos em sistemas corporativos e escassez de validações em cenários reais.	"The existing literature review indicates the growing adoption of AI in enterprise systems. However, the application of AI is confined to non-generative AI approaches. [...] Lack of efficient adaptation of transformer models in enterprise systems."